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THE EFFECT OF FATIGUE DAMAGE ON VISCOELASTIC PROPERTIES OF ANGLE-PLY GFRP LAMINATES

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- Introduction
- Motivation
- Methodology
- Results and discussion
- Conclusion

Inputs and preprocessing:

- Input the initial mechanical properties including viscoelastic and strengths of material in lamina level for fiber, matrix and shear direction
- Preprocessing for variable amplitude loading using Rainflow Algorithm

Time-dependent failure and degradation:

- Hashin and energy-based failure criteria
- Degradation rules for strength and stiffness of material

Cycle-dependent failure and degradation:

- Hashin failure criterion
- Residual strength model
- Residual stiffness model

Schapery viscoelastic law:

$$\varepsilon(t) = g_0 S_0 \sigma(t) + g_1 \int_0^t \sum_{k=1}^n S_k (1 - e^{-\lambda_k (\psi - \psi')}) \frac{dg_2 \sigma}{d\tau} d\tau$$

Constitutive law for lamina using Schapery law:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{11}(t) \\ \varepsilon_{22}(t) \\ \gamma_{12}(t) \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} & 0 \\ S_{21} & g_{0,22} S_{0,22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & g_{0,66} S_{0,66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{11}(t) \\ \sigma_{22}(t) \\ \tau_{12}(t) \end{Bmatrix} + \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 0 \\ g_{1,22} \int_0^t \sum_{k=1}^n S_{k,22} (1 - e^{-\lambda_{k,22} (\psi - \psi')}) \frac{dg_{2,22} \sigma_{22}}{d\tau} d\tau \\ g_{1,66} \int_0^t \sum_{k=1}^n S_{k,66} (1 - e^{-\lambda_{k,66} (\psi - \psi')}) \frac{dg_{2,66} \tau_{12}}{d\tau} d\tau \end{array} \right\}$$

Creep-fatigue interaction:

- Modeling time-dependent (viscoelastic) properties in terms of fatigue damage level under loading
- Modeling viscoelastic deformation effect on cycle-dependent properties (fatigue stiffness, strength)

Creep-fatigue interaction:

Recovery-fatigue interaction:

(Movahedi-rad, et al., 2019)

- **Cycle-dependent properties:**
 - Study the effect of relatively large deformation caused by viscoelastic behavior on S-N curves
 - Investigate quantitatively the effect of fiber reorientation as a result of creep deformation to refine residual stiffness models
- **Time-dependent properties:**
 - Modeling the evolution of viscoelastic properties depends on the state of damage caused by fatigue
 - Using the failed specimen to cut damaged sample for DMA testing and adopting TTSP to obtain creep master curves
- **Testing:**
 - Quasi-static tests
 - CA Fatigue tests
 - DMA tests

■ Fabrication:

- Specimen layup: $[\pm 45]_{2s}$
- Material: Glass/epoxy
- Method: Vacuum infusion

■ Measurements:

- DIC
- IR thermal camera

■ Testing:

- Quasi-static tests
- CA Fatigue tests
- DMA tests

S0.52_R0.1

S0.46_R0.1

- DMA testing for Temperature in range of 35 to 115 °C and frequency sweeps
- Single Cantilever Fixture

- Modeling time-dependent (viscoelastic) properties in terms of fatigue damage level under loading
- Increasing Damping ratio and decreasing T_{α}
- The Modulus values for DMA testing and Fatigue stiffness comparable

- Creep-recovery tests with 60 and 30 minutes for creep and recovery parts
- TTSP for the temperatures range from 35 to 115 °C

- Modeling viscoelastic properties in terms of fatigue damage
- Besides the vertical shift observing by fatigue stiffness degradation, we have considerable horizontal shift
- Feasibly developing an extension of TTSP, called time-temperature-fatigue damage to model evolution of viscoelastic properties for different fatigue damage level

- Modeling viscoelastic properties and shifting factor in terms of fatigue damage state
- Besides the vertical shift observing by fatigue stiffness degradation, we have considerable horizontal shift
- Feasibly developing an extension of TTSP, called time-temperature-fatigue damage to model evolution of viscoelastic properties for different fatigue damage level

(a)

(b)

DMA Sample ID	Storage modulus (MPa)	Damping Ratio	T _g	D = 1-(E/E ₀)	H Shift Factor (a _T)	V Shift Factor (b _e)
S0.52_a	4810	0.0498	75	0.3663	-2.3	0.16
S0.52_b	5125	0.4839	78	0.3248	-2.2	0.15
S0.46_a	5480	0.0462	80	0.2780	-1.6	0.12
S0.46_b	7030	0.0304	82	0.0738	-1.1	0.09
Undamaged	7600	0.0255	85	--	--	--

- Conducting DMA tests on damaged and undamaged material to study the effect of fatigue damage on viscoelastic properties
- Distinguish the more severe damage under higher stress level and effect on viscoelastic properties
- Suggesting to develop TTSFD principle, to obtain viscoelastic properties depends on damage state as observed for higher stress level we observed more vertical and horizontal shifts
- Completing the DMA tests for other R-ratios and stress levels to finally model generalized residual viscoelastic properties
- Developing the suitable viscoelastic model to capture time-dependent deformations for FEM and extending in PDM of elastic material to viscoelastic

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Thanks for your attention!

- Hashin failure criterion:

$$\text{Fiber failure in tension : } 1 = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{\sigma_A^+} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{\tau_A} \right)^2$$

$$\text{Fiber failure in compression : } 1 = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{-\sigma_A^-} \right)^2$$

$$\text{Matrix failure in tension : } 1 = \left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{\sigma_T^+} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{\tau_A} \right)^2$$

$$\text{Matrix failure in compression : } 1 = \left[\left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{2\tau_T} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{\tau_A} \right)^2 \right] + \left[\left[\left(\frac{\sigma_T^-}{2\tau_T} \right)^2 - 1 \right] \frac{\sigma_{22}}{\sigma_T^-} \right]$$

- Reiner–Weissenberg failure criterion (R-W):

$$\varepsilon(t) = g_0 S_0 \sigma(t) + g_1 \int_0^t \sum_{k=1}^n S_k (1 - e^{-\lambda_k (\psi - \psi')}) \frac{dg_2 \sigma}{d\tau} d\tau$$

$$\psi = \int_0^t \frac{dt'}{a_\sigma}, \psi' = \psi(\tau) \int_0^\tau \frac{dt'}{a_\sigma}$$

$$\varepsilon_{k,ij}(t) = S_{k,ij} \int_0^t (1 - e^{-\lambda_{k,ij}(\psi - \psi')}) \frac{d(g_{2,ij} \sigma_{ij})}{d\tau} d\tau$$

$$\varepsilon_{ij}(t) = g_{0,ij} S_{0,ij} \sigma_{ij}(t) + g_{1,ij} \sum_{k=1}^n \varepsilon_{k,ij}(t)$$

$$w_{s,ij}(t) \approx g_{0,ij} S_{0,ij} \frac{[\sigma_{ij}(t)]^2}{2} + g_{1,ij} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{g_{2,ij} S_{k,ij}} \frac{[\varepsilon_{k,ij}(t)]^2}{2}$$

Cycle-dependent properties: S-N Curves

- Fiber reorientation for S0.63-R0.5
- Dashed line: Not- considering deformation
- Solid Line: Excluding the effect of fiber reorientation

Cycle-dependent properties: Fatigue Stiffness

- Fiber reorientation for S0.63-R0.5
- DIC $\Delta\theta_{av} = \arctan\left(\frac{1+\varepsilon_x}{1-\varepsilon_y}\right) - 45$

